

Deep Learning Approaches for Spectrum Sensing in Cognitive Radio Networks

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Abstract—The number of network devices continues to rise as we advance towards 6G communication systems. A new range of frequencies is allocated while the earlier resources remain underutilized. Cognitive Radio (CR) enables the dynamic spectrum management of frequencies while detecting the unoccupied bands with the aid of spectrum sensing. By adopting Deep Learning (DL) for spectrum sensing, the performance of the 6G networks can be made more robust. This paper presents a survey of several DL algorithms such as, Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks and combination of CNNs and LSTMs that have been applied for performing spectrum sensing. The application of DL to spectrum sensing is then demonstrated by considering it as a binary classification problem. An MLP with its hyperparameters optimized by using Grid Search algorithm is proposed to classify a dataset consisting of RadioML 2018.01A and noise samples with high accuracy.

Keywords— *Artificial Intelligence (AI), Cognitive Radio, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Deep Learning, Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Networks, Spectrum Sensing, Spectrum Sharing, 6G*

I. INTRODUCTION

With the advent of the smartphone and high-speed internet, the demand for radio spectrum is continuously increasing and has resulted in the shortage of spectrum resources [1], [2], [3]. According to Ericsson's estimate [4], by the end of 2027, there will be about 8.9 billion mobile subscriptions. Currently the spectrum bands are under-utilized due to fixed allocation techniques that allow only licensed users to utilize the assigned spectrum despite the spectrum being free [5]. Although static spectrum management techniques assist in overcoming interference, an exponential

increase in the number of network devices will however exhaust the radio resources. Furthermore, urgent radio requirements can be denied while multiple bands remain underutilized. Dynamic Spectrum Management (DSM) is a flexible approach which allows multiple services to operate in a single band. With DSM, the spectrum of licensed Primary Users (PUs) can be shared with the unlicensed Secondary Users (SUs) when PUs are inactive. By setting up DSM, the spectrum requirement can be reduced significantly from 76 GHz to 19 GHz [6], in the presence of billions of Internet of Things (IoT) devices. Cognitive Radio (CR) is the main enabling approach for DSM [7]. The spectrum sensing function of a CR identifies the availability of PU's radio resources so that the vacant frequency bands can be used by SUs.

This work first describes the concepts of CR and spectrum sensing. Most of the previous research works on spectrum sensing are focused on conventional algorithms and traditional Machine Learning (ML) techniques used for sensing the primary spectrum. In this paper spectrum sensing algorithms based on DL approaches are discussed and their architectures are summarized. In addition, the drawbacks of conventional spectrum sensing methods are highlighted. This work further proposes a DL architecture which by treating spectrum sensing as a binary classification problem detects the presence or absence of PU.

The paper organization is as follows. Section I introduces the problem of spectrum scarcity and the concept of DSM. Section II provides details about CR and spectrum sensing approaches. Section III describes various deep learning-based spectrum sensing approaches. Section IV and V include simulation results and discussion respectively while VI concludes this paper.

II. COGNITIVE RADIO AND SPECTRUM SENSING

A. Basics of Cognitive Radio (CR)

CR is a configurable and programmable device that adapts its transmission parameters intelligently based on the radio environment and its internal states and provides system users with the capability to utilize and share the spectrum opportunistically [8]. Fig. 1. depicts the basic features of a cognitive cycle. Below are the four key operations [9] within a CR network.

- 1) *Spectrum Sensing*: This function involves continuous sensing of PU's spectrum to determine unoccupied frequency bands also called as spectrum holes.
- 2) *Spectrum Sharing*: This step coordinates between the SUs that want to access the spectrum and prevents collisions.
- 3) *Spectrum Decision*: This task of CR determines the appropriate spectrum band which meets the quality of service and communication demands of users.
- 4) *Spectrum Mobility*: It ensures smooth handover of SUs from a spectrum hole to another with no interruptions.

B. Spectrum Sensing Approaches

Spectrum sensing is the crucial function of CR [10]. It is formulated as a binary hypothesis testing problem with the presence or absence of the PU signal [11]. Sensing of the PU spectrum is traditionally achieved with the help of popular sensing methods such as Energy Detection (ED), Matched Filter Detection (MFD), Cyclostationary Based Detection (CBD) and Eigenvalue Based Detection (EBD) and the performance of these above-mentioned algorithms is assessed by the probability of false alarm (P_{fa}) and probability of detection (P_d) [10]. When multiple SUs cooperate to improve the accuracy of sensing either by sharing their data or sensing decisions, it is known as Cooperative Spectrum Sensing (CSS).

ED technique does not need any prior knowledge of the PU signal but suffers from high false alarm rates and performs poorly at low Signal-to-Noise Ratios (SNRs) [12]. MFD is impractical as it requires prior knowledge of PU [13]. CBD is complex and slow [14] while EBD involves complex computations [10]. Due to the problem of missed detection of the PU and false alarm, the conventional spectrum sensing methods lead to inefficient utilization of radio resources [15].

ML, which is a subset of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has gained immense popularity recently and is being used to solve a range of research problems. ML has also been deployed for the task of sensing the radio spectrum. Previous research works [9], [12], [14] summarize the use of traditional ML algorithms like support vector machines, naive bayes and K-nearest neighbor to reduce the sensing time. These algorithms predict the Radio Frequency (RF) channel status with the help of energy or probability vectors by treating spectrum sensing as a binary classification problem [12]. However, the manual feature extraction process in these techniques is time consuming and requires field experts. This feature selection in ML algorithms impacts the detection rate [9].

Deep Learning (DL) is a branch of ML. It is a data driven approach that is capable of automatically capturing complex

Fig. 1. Basic Cognitive Cycle [17]

data features and patterns [16]. These algorithms are robust to uncertain radio environments as they are quickly adaptable. By optimally utilizing the non-linear relationship in the training data, DL enhances the model performance [18]. DL based spectrum sensing algorithms can be classified based on their architecture as: Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Networks and combination of CNNs and LSTMs. The next section presents a compilation of works which have deployed DL for spectrum sensing.

III. DEEP LEARNING BASED APPROACHES TO SPECTRUM SENSING

A. Multilayer Perceptrons (MLPs)

MLPs are the simplest feedforward neural networks which contain one or more hidden layers between the input and output layers. MLPs having two or more hidden layers qualify as a DL network. Fig. 2. Shows an MLP with 'n' hidden layers. In [19], an MLP consisting of three hidden layers is used in a CSS scenario to predict whether the PU is present or absent based on a dataset of geodesic distances obtained from the covariance matrices of noise and sensing signals. The proposed method was assessed in a scenario involving multiple signals and it was observed that for a fixed P_{fa} , a higher number of SUs results in better sensing performance. It was further observed by fixing the P_{fa} and using two SUs that the P_d is greater for intervals when SNR is high.

B. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)

CNNs are a class of deep neural networks which are widely used in the domain of computer vision. Fig. 3. Shows the basic CNN architecture. The common hidden layers in these networks are convolutional, rectified linear unit, and pooling layers that help in learning the main features and classification layers [20]. CNNs are widely adopted for a range of spectrum sensing problems due to the similarity between signal covariance matrices and images [16].

In [21], a CNN-based model termed 'Deep Cooperative Sensing' (DCS) is proposed. The sensing data is generated by

Fig. 2. Architecture of a simple MLP with n hidden layers

Fig. 3. Basic CNN Architecture

multiple SUs to detect the status of PU. DCS which has three convolutional and two fully connected layers can combine sensing results from SUs irrespective of whether they are hard or soft decisions. The model gives robust performance even when the count of SUs or training samples is low or in conditions of high noise power density.

In [22], a CNN having a single convolutional layer is used to perform data fusion in a CSS scenario with five SUs. The generated dataset consists of Binary Phase Shift Keying (BPSK) modulated random bits modelled to incorporate Rayleigh and Nakagami- m fading. In a condition of high noise floor, the results are compared with ED based hard fusion rules of AND, majority rules and OR. The performance of the CNN surpasses that of AND and majority rules.

In [11], a CNN model with residual blocks is designed by treating spectrum sensing as a two-class classification problem. The powers of received signals are normalized and power spectrum is given as an input to the CNN. The signal data of eight modulation types: BPSK, Quadrature Phase Shift Keying (QPSK), 2-Frequency Shift Keying (2FSK), 4FSK, 16- Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (16QAM), 32QAM, 4-Pulse Amplitude Modulation (4PAM), and 8PAM and the noise data are generated through simulation. Besides comparing the performance of the CNN with two traditional spectrum sensing methods, the authors simulated 8PSK, 8FSK and 64QAM signals to test the capability of the model to detect unknown signals. The model is also evaluated against real-world Aircraft Communications Addressing and Reporting System (ACARS) signals by following a transfer learning- based approach. The model maintains robust performance even in the presence of coloured (pink) noise.

In [23], a CNN with two convolutional and two dense layers referred to as ‘Deep Sensing’ takes the filtered and sampled radio signals simulated in MATLAB as input and decides the status of PU. Deep Sensing was not efficient when applied to a communication scenario which differs from the training data and thus experiments were performed with transfer learning without labelled data and with fine tuning. The model was found to be robust across various domains when a small amount of labelled data is available.

Authors in [24] propose ‘Deep-CRNet’ which performs opportunistic spectrum access-based sensing for SUs in a communication network of IoTs and unmanned aerial vehicles. Complex waveforms of both the PU signal and noise are generated synthetically. The classification architecture comprises of 85 layers and has convolution and residual-inception blocks achieving an accuracy of 99.74%. The model is also used to classify over the air (OTA) signals by using RadioML dataset and it outperforms other state-of-the-art approaches.

In [25], Amplitude Shift Keying (ASK) and FSK signals are artificially generated with the help of an Arduino Uno card and a 433 MHz wireless transmitter. These signals are captured by an RTL-SDR and are generated for a variety of distances between sender and receiver. These are then classified with the help of CNN having two convolutional layers as either PU signal or noise signal.

C. Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Networks

Although widely used for spectrum sensing, CNNs cannot capture long term time dependencies of the input data [17]. LSTMs are a type of recurrent neural networks capable of capturing the temporal details from a sequence. Fig. 4. shows a simple LSTM network and an LSTM cell. In [26], the temporal correlation within the spectrum data acquired through an empirical setup is exploited with the help of an LSTM network. PU activity statistics: on duration, off duration and duty cycle are calculated. Data at very low SNR is included to make the LSTM unbiased. The validation accuracy is found to be maximum for LSTM having single hidden unit. LSTM based Spectrum Sensing (LSTM-SS) and PU Activity Statistics-based Spectrum Sensing (PAS-SS) models are proposed. Two empirical bed setups are used in which data is acquired through a universal software radio peripheral and a digital spectrum analyzer respectively.

D. Combination of CNNs and LSTMs

A CNN can capture spatial variations in the network input while an LSTM gathers the temporal changes in the data. Fig. 5. shows a basic CNN-LSTM model. To leverage the advantages of both CNNs and LSTMs, [15] proposes a DL based model called ‘DLSenseNet’ that uses the RadioML2016.10b dataset and detects the presence of PU. The DLSenseNet model consists of a modified inception block. LSTM and fully connected layers are added to the convolutional layers of the inception block. An LSTM layer is added to capture temporal dependencies of data.

The work [28] utilizes a DL model consisting of two convolutional layers and an LSTM layer followed by a dense layer which learns the energy correlation features and PU

Fig. 4. An LSTM cell [27] and a simple LSTM architecture

Fig. 5. Basic structure of a CNN-LSTM model

activity pattern from the sensing data to predict the presence or absence of the PU.

To overcome the SNR- Wall issue of the conventional energy detectors, [29] proposes ‘DetectNet’ – a neural network comprising of convolutional, LSTM and fully connected layers to perform spectrum sensing. The positive samples are generated in eight modulation schemes BPSK, QPSK, 8PSK, Continuous Phase Frequency Shift Keying (CPFSK), QAM16, QAM64, Gaussian Frequency Shift Keying (GFSK) and PAM4 by following the RadioML2016.10a dataset while the negative samples are additive noises based on zero mean circularly symmetric complex Gaussian distribution. In addition, ‘SoftCombinationNet’ is presented for cooperative sensing scenarios which combines the soft information from each sensing node to provide a global decision.

Motivated by the fact that a BiLSTM can make complete use of the hidden states by scanning data in opposite directions simultaneously, [16] proposes a deep neural network comprising of convolutional, BiLSTM and self-attention layers for classifying primary signal data generated using GNU Radio. This architecture performs decently when training and testing modulation schemes are different.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

To test the efficacy of DL algorithms for sensing the presence or absence of PU, we perform experiments with an MLP, which is the simplest DL architecture. This MLP architecture predicts the spectrum state by performing binary classification of a dataset consisting of PU signals and noise

signals. To create our dataset and represent the PU signals, 50,000 signal frames are randomly chosen after shuffling the RadioML 2018.01A dataset [30], [31]. RadioML 2018.01A consists of synthetic simulated channel effects and over-the-air recordings of 24 types of digital and analog modulation in the SNR range of -20 dB to +20 dB. This data is in the form of complex I/Q frames and each frame has a sample length of 1024. Equal number of I/Q frames of noise following standard normal distribution are generated in Python to represent absence of PU. This dataset consisting of equal number of signal and noise samples is then used to train an MLP which predicts the presence or absence of PU. The 100,000 samples of the dataset are split into training, validation, and test sets in the ratio of 80:10:10.

The design of the MLP is finalized with the help of Grid Search technique which is used to optimize the number of hidden layers, number of neurons, activation functions and dropout rates for each hidden layer, batch size, number of epochs and learning rate. The proposed architecture and the optimized hyperparameters help achieve an optimal model performance and are summarized in figure 6 and Table I. Our proposed architecture consists of 4 hidden layers with number of neurons in each hidden layer being 256, 128, 64 and 32 respectively. These layers have ‘relu’ activation and no dropout. Each dataset frame is of dimensions 1024*2 as each frame consists of I/Q values with length 1024. Each frame is flattened to a size of 2048 to provide input to the MLP.

The model is trained for 20 epochs with a batch size of 16 and a learning rate of 0.001. The model is optimized using ‘Adam’ optimizer and the loss is evaluated with the help of ‘binary_crossentropy’. The MLP quickly learns to efficiently differentiate between the signal and noise classes. The accuracy and loss curves of the MLP with the optimum values of the hyperparameters for training and validation sets are shown in figures 7 and 8. The accuracy and loss curves of the validation set closely follow that of training set and the model achieves a high classification accuracy of 98.55% on the test data. Table II sums up the performance of our architecture with the help of commonly used evaluation metrics of accuracy, recall score, precision score and F1 score. The model misclassifies only a small fraction of PU signal and noise signal samples as depicted in the confusion matrix in figure 9.

V. DISCUSSION

Spectrum sensing is a challenging problem due to the presence of phenomena such as multipath fading and noise uncertainty shadowing in a wireless system which make the identification of PU state difficult [13]. DL algorithms can automatically learn features from data rather than depending on signal features and hence reduce the risk of incorrect sensing [15]. MLPs due to their simple architectures and CNNs due to the correlations in sensing outcomes are preferred to fuse the sensing data from multiple SUs in a CSS scenario. In non-CSS scenarios, both CNNs and LSTMs are widely used with diverse and complex radio data to capture the spatial and temporal details of sensing data efficiently.

In this paper, we experimented with the simplest DL architecture with the help of RadioML 2018.01A dataset and

Fig. 6. Design of proposed MLP based classifier

Hyperparameter	Grid	Optimum Value
Number of hidden layers	[2,3,4,5]	4
Hidden layer nodes	[512, 256, 128, 64, 32, 16]	256, 128, 64, 32
Hidden layer activation function	['sigmoid', 'relu', 'tanh']	'relu' for all hidden layers
Dropout rates for hidden layers	[0.0,0.2,0.4,0.8]	0.0 for all hidden layers
Batch size	[8, 16, 32, 64]	16
Number of epochs	[10,20,30]	20
Learning rate	[0.001,0.01,0.1]	0.001

Fig. 7. Plot for training and validation accuracies

Fig. 8. Plot for training and validation loss

Metric	Value
Accuracy	98.55%
Recall Score	98.69%
Precision Score	98.43%
F1 Score	98.56%

Fig. 9. Confusion matrix

synthetically generated noise. The proposed MLP model differentiated signal samples having SNR values in the range of -20 dB to +20 dB and 24 different modulation types from noise samples with a high accuracy.

Although DL based approaches are gaining popularity to perform spectrum sensing, these algorithms require large amount of data for training. Thus, the major challenge of deploying DL algorithms is the lack of comprehensive RF datasets [30]. Transfer learning can be a promising approach in cases when limited amount of training data is available. The performance of the above-mentioned algorithms should be validated using real world datasets [9].

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Being the main enabler of DSM, CR technology enables the SUs to access the unutilized bands of licensed users and helps address the issue of scarcity of spectrum resources. This paper discussed the concepts of CR and spectrum sensing. The drawbacks of conventional spectrum sensing, and traditional ML algorithms were highlighted. While the conventional sensing techniques suffer from the issue of missed detection of the PU and false alarm, traditional ML approaches require manual feature extraction. Further, spectrum sensing approaches based on DL classes of MLP, CNN, LSTM and combination of CNN and LSTM along with their architectures were summarized. These DL algorithms with their ability to extract features in an automated manner and adaptability to changing radio environment are increasingly being deployed for the task of sensing the PU spectrum. We demonstrated the application of an MLP on a dataset comprising of signal samples from RadioML 2018.01A dataset and noise samples generated in Python. The classifier achieved a test accuracy of 98.55%. In future, the performance of our model will be tested against real world data. CNN and LSTM architectures will be further explored to capture the spatial and temporal

information from data. This work also discussed the challenges in using DL techniques for identification of vacant frequency bands and the need for new and diverse RF datasets.

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